

Private school teachers' voice in the Philippines amidst Covid-19 pandemic: A descriptive phenomenological study

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ABSTRACT

Several studies discovered that private teachers have a higher probability of losing their jobs than public school teachers during the Global Financial Crisis. This appears to be the case in many low- and middle-income countries throughout the current crisis or covid-19 pandemic. This phenomenon is generating a lot of problems, particularly as voiced out by private school teachers in the context of developing countries. This motivates the researcher to investigate and discuss the problems faced by private school teachers in the Philippines in the wake of the Covid-19 crisis. Specifically, the researcher described their motivation factors teaching in the private school and their challenges during a Covid-19 pandemic. The researcher used a descriptive phenomenological research approach and an in-depth interview. Using purposive sampling, seven (7) participants were selected to participate in the study. To preserve the confidentiality of the research participants, ethical measures were also implemented. The responses of the participants were thematically analyzed using Colaizzi's methods of descriptive phenomenology. Results revealed 3 themes on the motivation factors: Passion in Teaching, Teaching as a Calling and Promotion in Public School and 5 themes related to challenges which include Financial Constraints, Mental Health Issues, Working beyond Contract, Lack of Teaching Resources and Poor Relationship with the School Heads. Indeed, private teachers are also encountering problems that need to be addressed by the national government. As voiced out by the participants they received nothing from the government as compared to the public teachers during the pandemic. This study recommends that the national government must also look at how to help private teachers who are affected by the pandemic, such as financial assistance. Private school institutions may also consider creating policies to address some issues encountered by their employees.

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INTRODUCTION

Teachers' function is to guide students in learning by acquiring information and creating an environment where the students can learn effectively. Indeed, many teachers set themselves the goal of being the best educator they can be. It's incredibly satisfying to impart knowledge to the students and work with them to ensure that they grasp not only theories but also practical applications. In the study of Beauchamp & Thomas (2009) discussed that teaching is different from other professions, teaching can be defined as a noble profession which needs self-sacrifice and dedication or commitment as contrasting to being simply a source of income. Furthermore, teachers strive to inspire students in all parts of their lives, and many teachers consider themselves as role models since it is part of their work. In fact, students recognized their teachers as their role models who helped them to improve their academic performance (Bashir et al. 2014). A role model is somebody who motivates and inspires students to achieve excellence, and who teaches them how to succeed in life and become the best they can be through experience and perseverance (Narinasamy & Logeswaran, 2015).

In the Philippines, as well in other countries teachers are employed in public or private schools. A private teacher is an educator who works in a private school setting. They can work in a private institution at the elementary, middle, and high school levels, giving students specialized or general training. The licensing requirements for employment are one aspect that distinguishes the private school teachers from those of public school teachers. Private schools are more flexible with licensure but rather focus their recruitment on qualified and accredited individuals, while public schools requires teacher applicants to have a teaching license in their profession. As the Philippine education sector pursued their goals, building and teaching students to become good contributors for the country's development. Unforeseen events occurred where Covid-19 virus had a huge impact on the world economy and even the educational sector. As the Covid-19 virus spread, primary and secondary schools, as well as universities, were forced to close in several nations, affecting 1.5 billion students (UNESCO, 2020). Educators worldwide rushed to switch to online instruction in the hopes of recovering the academic year. Universities in China have shifted their teaching methods from traditional face-to-face instruction to online learning or teaching in order to achieve the goal of "nonstop teaching and learning." (Bao, 2020). In the Philippines, the Education department pursued learning continuity on October 5, 2020, rather than August 2020, as originally planned. Face-to-face learning engagement is prohibited, which is why the Department of Education (DepEd) uses modular and remote learning modalities to guarantee student safety while learning through employing printed or digital modules, online learning materials, radio and television-based instructions (DepEd, 2020). In the study of Kopelman and Rosen (2016) public versus private school teacher job loss over time, discovered that private school teachers in the United States have a higher probability of losing their jobs than public school teachers during both recessionary and non-recessionary periods, with the gap increasing during the Global Financial Crisis. This appears to be the case in many low- and middle-income countries throughout the current crisis or covid-19 pandemic, based on recent data.

Living with Covid-19 pandemic is a new experience for people, and the current literature on the pandemic does not clearly reveal the underlying ambiguity and complexity of private teachers experiences to this unanticipated situation. Based on the stories shared by the private teachers in social media and through an exhaustive literature review, the researcher was able to determine the gap. It is reported by the private school teachers that they are facing difficulties during this pandemic which they receive less support and attention from the Philippine government, some private teachers are being laid off and some of them are receiving low salary as compared before pandemic due to the impact of this worldwide crisis on private school institutions. Most of the studies conducted about the challenges of teachers are only focused to the public school teachers. It is true that public teachers, health workers and law enforce are facing difficulties during this worldwide crisis but private teachers with fixed-term contracts who are frequently hired locally are also struggling on how to cope with the abrupt transitions of educational system in the Philippines. This is the reason why the researcher conducted this study to give voice for the private teachers during pandemic.

OBJECTIVES

The study is conceptualized to seek and understand the lived experiences of private school teachers amidst pandemic. Specifically to:

1. Determine the motivation factors of private teachers in teaching private school.
2. Explore and describe the challenges encountered by private teachers during pandemic.

METHODS

Research Design

The research design used was descriptive phenomenology. Individuals' lived experiences are explored and described using descriptive phenomenology which usually employed in social science research (Dela Fuente, 2021). The primary objective for conducting qualitative research is to discover and understand what is underlying any phenomena about which little is known.

Participants

The researcher invited seven private teachers who are currently teaching in private schools during pandemic.

Instrument

The researcher employed interviews to collect the necessary information. Interviews were utilized to gain a 'deeper' understanding of phenomena than would be obtained using simply quantitative measures, such as questionnaires. In particular, a semi-structured interview was used in the study, which included many important questions that helped to define the areas to be investigated while also allowing the interviewer and interviewee to deviate in order to pursue an idea or response in further detail.

Data Collection

A semi-structured in-depth interview was the primary method utilized to gather data and obtain reliable and factual information as used by Dela Fuente (2019). Each interview was conducted face-to-face and lasted 20-30 minutes. The interview started with general questions but was followed by a relaxed and adaptable approach. The level of engagement of the participants was the most important factor in the interview process.

Ethical Consideration

The participants were informed that the study was totally voluntary, and that they may withdraw at any time with no consequences to their job performance. All participants signed written consent forms before the interview began. The researcher did every effort to concede and keep the rights, interests, and sensitivities of the participants of the study as part of ethical considerations. Confidentiality was ensured by using code names to replace participant names on transcripts. The audio data was saved on a computer laptop with a password that was kept in a secure folder and only available for the researcher.

Data Analysis

Interviews were transcribed verbatim and analysed using Colaizzi's approach. The analysis based on Colaizzi's method included the following seven steps: (1) reading all the transcripts three to five times to gain an understanding of meanings conveyed; (2) reviewing each description and extracting significant statements; (3) formulating meanings for these significant statements; (4) categorising the formulated meanings into clusters of

themes; (5) integrating the findings into an exhaustive description of the phenomenon; (6) returning the exhaustive description to participants for validation of feelings; (7) incorporate relevant data in the final description of phenomenon.

FINDINGS

This section showed the different themes that was obtained from the analysis of the data gathered through a face to face interview. The researcher made every effort to protect the participants by using code names in transcribing the audio recorded interview. The significant statements from the transcribed data were extracted followed by formulation of meanings based on the significant statements. The researcher also categorized the formulated meanings into cluster of themes and main themes were formulated. Using Colaizzi’s Methods in descriptive phenomenology, the researcher was able to get the main themes that presented the motivation factors and challenges of private teachers amidst pandemic. This section presents the lived experiences of private teachers using the themes obtained with the significant statements of the participants to provide the depth and richness of their motivation factors in teaching in a private school and their challenges amidst covid-19 pandemic.

Table 1. Shows the three (3) main themes under the motivation factors of private teachers in teaching private school

Main Themes
Passion in Teaching
Teaching as a Calling
Promotion in Public School

Theme 1: Passion in Teaching

Passion is essential in fostering a good learning atmosphere that is conducive to successful learning and teaching. Student learning may be influenced by a teacher's passion. Teaching with passion enhances learning because it inspires students to participate in learning process. In order to be a successful teacher, you must be passionate about what you are doing. According to the participants, they love to teach because it is their passion. Jane shared that:

“I love teaching, this is my passion. There are many opportunities waiting for me, outside of this profession but I chose to stay in teaching even in a private school only simply because I love what I am doing”

She also added:

“Yeah, there are many opportunities, like to be a policewoman but teaching makes me more satisfied as I continue my existence in this world”

Shane also emphasized that teaching is a calling and there’s nothing bad in pursuing teaching profession in a private school. She said:

“Teaching is not just a profession but it is a calling...I love what I am doing, and there’s nothing wrong teaching in a private school”

Sheila expressed that she loves teaching even though she is in a private school, she is more happy in teaching every moment she sees the smiles of her students. She said:

“I love my students, I care for them, that’s why I am still in teaching, yeah this is a private school but it is not about where you teach but it is how you give value on your profession”

She added:

“What makes me more in love in teaching, are my students, I love their smiles, and it makes me happy knowing that I am the reason of those smiles”

Jake also shared that teaching is about touching the lives of other people not for him to be a rich man someday. He said:

“I chose teaching not be rich someday, but to touch the lives of young ones, I want them to grow with good attitude, I want them to see the beauty of life and this only be possible through teaching them. I love them”

Keith had this to share:

“Staying and teaching in a private school doesn’t make you a teacher, same with teachers in public. It is not about the status of your job, but it is how you love your work while building the lives of your students”

She added:

“I stay in private school because it makes me happy”

Theme 2: Teaching as a Calling

A job might be almost anything. People get paid to do the most outlandish things. A calling, on the other hand, is something more than a job. It is a God-given conviction for a certain goal or action. Teachers make more sacrifices for their students than most people know, whether it's their time after school or their own money to provide some classroom materials. In terms of salary, the lowest pay is frequently provided in private teachers as compared to public teachers. Some participants explained that teaching is a calling not just a profession. Shane explained that teaching in a private school is a calling not just a job only. She said:

“In spite of having low salary in a private school, I stayed in teaching simply because I know it is a calling from above”

She added:

“This is not a job only but I consider it as a calling Sir”

Jane also explained that teaching is not just for her to earn money but to touch the lives of others. She said:

“Teaching is not just a profession but a calling that I must teach not just to earn money but to really touch other’s lives to be the person they want to be... I am more passionate to teach every time I think that I am part of other’s lives”

She added:

“I want to show to my students, that I am with them, in achieving their goals in life”

Keith also had to share:

“Teaching in a private school doesn’t mean you are lower than a public teacher, I stayed in teaching simply because I know that this is more than a profession, I did not leave teaching simply because I am called to be a teacher”

She added:

“Even though this is a private school, there’s nothing difference with the public schools aside of salary, yet it is both calling to teach”

Theme 3: Promotion in Public School

Experience in teaching is necessary in any school institutions, this is needed in order to be hired in private or public schools in the Philippines. Applying in a public school, teacher applicants must undergo in process, and should meet the criteria set by the Department of Education. Interview, teaching experience, proficiency examination, education and attended trainings are needed as part of the application in public schools. Some participants described that they are teaching in private schools for them to have points and have experience in teaching to be qualified in a government or public school. Jessica shared that:

“I chose to teach in private school in order for me to get points as part in ranking system of public schools, I have to get experience in teaching”

She added:

“Everyone wants to be in public school, but there’s no shortcut in achieving that dream but to undergo or have an experience first in teaching”

Kyle explained that he is teaching in private school for an additional experience and for him to be hired in public school. He said:

“To be hired in public schools, we must possess an experience in teaching, that’s why I chose to teach in private school, to have more points in ranking system of the Department of Education”

He added:

“My family wants me to be an army, but I want to pursue what I have finished that’s why I am teaching in private school as my first step”

Jake also shared that:

“It is true enough that teaching in a private school is good, but it is actually one of the process in applying for public school in order to be qualified you must have an experience in teaching”

He added:

“My mother wants me to leave my profession and go in army, but still I want to be in teaching”

Jackson explained that it is an opportunity for him to teach in a private school to get an experience in teaching before he proceed in public school. He said:

“I stay in private school for me to earn points, it is needed in application for Deped or in public school”

He added:

“So teaching in a private school is an opportunity for us to earn more points and to have experience in teaching”

Table 2. Shows the five (5) main themes under the challenges encountered by private teacher during pandemic

Main Themes
Financial Constraints
Mental Health Issues
Working Beyond Contract
Lack of Teaching Resources
Poor Relationship with the School Heads

Theme1: Financial Constraints

The Covid-19 pandemic has a massive effect on the world market economy and social relationships, forcing countries to suffer deeper economic slump. Poverty and worldwide social inequality have also grown as a result of the pandemic. Receiving low salary, burden on family needs, lesser number of student enrolees, possibility of schools' closure were shared by most of the participants. Jessica expressed that they are struggling in terms of financial matters. She said:

“I am struggling financially during this pandemic, we have low salary as compared to public teachers, but we have the same work and that is to teach students, reach out them during this pandemic sometimes I don't know where to get money for our daily needs in this pandemic”

She added:

“10,000 is not enough for a month, especially I have family to feed”

Sheila shared that living in this crisis time is difficult most especially private schools where they are teaching were affected by the pandemic causing recession on the number of students which their salaries depend on the students. She said:

“It is not easy to live in this pandemic era sir, yes we love teaching, but I think we deserve to be paid higher based on our efforts...our salary private teachers decreases due to the impact of pandemic, we have low number of enrolees and if affected our salary...I am suffering financially I don't know how to budget my salary in one month”

She added:

“The government should give us attention also, they should listen in our voice as private teachers, we need subsidy from the government during this pandemic”

Jackson described his burden as a private teacher which the pandemic caused a great negative impact on his profession. He said:

“I have children to feed, my salary is not enough, I am a private teacher the most affected during this pandemic, why? Our salary decreases just for our school not to close during pandemic because students preferred to study in public schools because it is cheaper than in private school”

He added:

“Hoping that the government will help us, in this time of crisis”

Kyle also had to share:

“I have difficulties in terms of money in this time, I am really struggling, sometimes I want to give up but I have to be strong for my family”

He added:

“We are also contributors in the growth of our economy, we are also moulders of future leaders, the government should increase us our salary or at least make a way to help us private teachers during pandemic because we are really struggling financially”

Theme 2: Mental Health Issues

Psychological issues aroused since the pandemic started. This crisis gives dilemmas to the people around the world which affects their mental health by thinking those problems. Feeling stressed and pressured in life, feeling alone, lack of sleep, crying day and night and feeling disappointed were described by some participants. Jane expressed that she is stressed thinking how to overcome the difficulties brought by this pandemic. She said:

“ I feel so stressed, I feel like I am nothing I don't know how to describe it but sometimes I am lack of sleep thinking how to survive in this pandemic...I am out of my mind sometimes ”

Jake voiced out his emotions and disappointment on himself thinking that he is not able to provide the needs of his family during this pandemic. He said:

“I am pressured in life in this time of crisis, seems like I am a failure...I cannot give what my family demands on me and that gives more pressure”

He added:

“It seems no one supports me in my battle”

Keith also shared that she is suffering from depression because of this pandemic. She said:

“Sometimes I cannot control my emotions, there were nights that I am depressed, and all I want to do is to be alone, thinking all my problems in life brought by this pandemic”

She added:

“I have to be strong but depression during pandemic is more powerful that sometimes I cannot control but to cry and cry day and night”

Shane also had to share:

“I cannot avoid thinking of my problems, I am weak, and this is because of I cannot give all my best for my family, I am stressed, depressed, loser, and I want to shout to release all my pains because of this covid-19 virus”

She added:

“Being a teacher is not that easy during pandemic, you are more pressured as compared to face to face...”

Theme 3: Working Beyond Contract

A contract is a written agreement between an employee and employer. It provides both the employee's and the company's rights and obligations. It can be implicit, verbal, or written, with a detailed actual contract that the employee signs. The terms of the agreement are determined by what was agreed upon until employee indicated that they would take the job. The participants expressed their struggles and pain as they work with their heads. Private teachers as voiced out by the participants are working beyond on their contract which gives them challenges on how to balance their responsibilities. Doing things that is not in the contract, performing different designations outside contract, feeling afraid, not being paid, not able to sleep due to extra paper works and contract must be followed were shared and described by the participants. Jackson is performing such tasks that are not on his contract. He said:

“I am doing things that is not actually in my contract, I am hired to teach subjects but not to do other works that is not in my contract”

He added:

“I am afraid not to do those things because that can be a ground for me not to be hired next school year”

Sheila also shared that she was given designations that is not part of her contract. She said:

“It is just too unfair that I have a lot of designations that is not in the contract I have signed, I do a lot of things that is not actually paid, this is my struggle in teaching”

She added:

“I chose to keep silent and doing things even that is not part of my job”

Shane shared that she get difficult on how to manage her tasks,

“You know what? There are things like some paper works, many tasks such as being coordinator in different areas. I don't know sometimes if what I have to finish first. I am not paid on those thing”

Keith expressed her pain on her services that is not paid. She said:

“We have unpaid services for the school, we cannot demand for payment of those services since it is not in our contract, but why do people I mean our head give us those tasks? Is it to test our commitment? That is too unfair! We do our job with passion then we deserve a good salary”

Jane described her effort just to finish the tasks assigned to her. She said:

“There are nights that I was not able to sleep sir, because there are tasks given by my supervisor that I have to finish, but actually it is her job to finish those things”

She added:

“Yeah I am just an employee...but I think I deserve to have an increase in my salary because I do a lot of things that was not in the agreement I signed Sir”

Jessica described her experience as a teacher that makes her feel stressed. She said:

“Contract must be followed but why it seems not...I work this, I work that, I do that, I do all things. I am not complaining sir but I feel so sad for myself. I feel so stressed”

Theme 4: Lack of Teaching Resources

Teaching amidst pandemic is not easy as what others think about it. Private teachers are mandated to teach their students virtually unlike in Public School that they purely adapted modular learning approach. In this case, private teachers must have their own gadgets or any technological resources in delivering their lessons via online. The participants are having difficulties due to lack of teaching resources which is connected to their financial problem. They cannot able to buy their own teaching resources due to financial constraints. Lack of gadgets, need to borrow laptop, struggling in making presentation and no budget to buy laptop and Wi-Fi for online discussion were shared and described by most of the participants. Sheila shared her problem. She said:

“In an online distance learning sir, we need gadgets or technological resources. I find it difficult because I don't have my own laptop which is very needed. I used my phone and sometimes I have to borrow laptop”

Jessica also shared her experience in online teaching. She said:

“I cannot deliver effectively the lessons because I'm just using my mobile data not a wifi...”

Shane explained:

“I am a newly hired teacher in private, I have no budget to buy laptop and wifi for online teaching”

Kyle also described his problem in making presentation for discussion. He said:

“One of my problems sir is that how to make power point presentation for my discussion that is really my struggle...I'm using my phone for discussion but my laptop is not functioning well”

Theme 5: Poor Relationship with the School Heads

There is a need for healthy relationships between teachers and school heads to ensure that they will work collaboratively to improve schools and sustain instructional quality. Poor collaborative planning might result from a

strained relationship between teachers and principals. The participants negatively described their relationships with their school heads which is one of their challenges in the teaching profession. Losing respect to the head, losing confidence, being embarrassed and humiliated by the head, no compassion at all and not a leader but a boss were shared and described by the participants. Kyle described how he lost his respect to their school head. He said:

“Our head is so strict...sometimes I understand but to the point that she is shouting us in most of the meeting...seems like I lost my respect to her”

Shane also shared her struggle in approaching their principal. She said:

“It is natural to a principal to get mad but I lost my confidence to talk with her because there was something she did to me...she embarrassed me in front of my colleagues”

She added:

“I don’t know how to approach her. I feel like I am always afraid to her that is one of my struggles Sir”

Jessica described that she is having difficulty on her workplace. She said:

“There was a time I was humiliated by our principal during the meeting. I kept silent but inside I’m broken, do you know that feeling Sir?”

She added:

“There’s no compassion at all it is too hard work in a place where there is hate”

Sheila described their relationship teachers with their principal. She said:

“Our principal is a boss not a leader she doesn’t know how to connect herself to us she make things complicated and always get mad to us that is my struggle no one can meet her standard”

DISCUSSIONS

This phenomenological study explored the lived experiences of private teachers during pandemic. The researcher extracted three main themes related to the motivation factors of teachers teaching in private school, five themes related to the challenges encountered by the private teachers amidst pandemic.

The result showed that private teachers chose to stay in the teaching profession and teach in a private school because of their passion in teaching. Indeed, effective teaching is founded on passion. Passion, which is essential for learning and teaching, enhances learning by fostering motivation and enthusiasm. Teachers that are interested in enhancing their students' learning potential strive to create successful learning environments. In connection, the study of Serin (2017) find out that teachers' passion in teaching is an important characteristic that can help students attain their goals. Teachers that are enthusiastic about their jobs can make a significant difference in their students' academic performance. Passion has a beneficial impact on learning and teaching by generating enthusiasm and action. In addition, the study of Gilal (2019) showed that through emotional contagion, a teacher's passion for teaching may be transmitted to a student's desire for work. Teachers can impact student performance simply by demonstrating their passion for teaching. This study also revealed that private teachers chose to teach in private school amidst pandemic because they believe that teaching is a calling. In the study of Na (2015) discussed that an effective teaching engagement and outcome are frequently based on the teacher's personal qualities, which

encompasses traits such as a good sense of humour, kindness, sympathy, compassion, caring, perseverance, and so on.

The teacher experiences a strong feeling of appreciation on a regular basis, which is a key link among these good traits. It is showed on their study that gratitude is among the most evident good feelings that may help a teacher's life and profession succeed. In reality, strategies for fostering appreciation for a teacher are provided, such as avoiding distractions, maintaining a gratitude diary, and maintaining a gratitude reminder. It is anticipated that with practice, teachers would be able to blend their sentiments to the cheerful channel and reach the point wherein teaching becomes a calling in their lives. The study of Alfun (2017) discussed that teacher commitment is an inner drive that motivates teachers to dedicate more time and attention in sustaining school participation. It is revealed on his study that commitment in teaching is a critical component to stay with boldness whatever difficulties a teacher may face in his/her profession. Teachers that are committed to the teaching profession are able to modify their teaching techniques to help students in the classroom. This study showed that private teachers chose to stay in private school because of points they can earn for promotion in public school. The Department of Education (DepEd) set a standard guidelines in hiring public teachers. Teaching experience is one of the guidelines that must be achieved by a teacher applicant. Education has 20 points, Teaching Experience has 15 points, Specialized Training and Skills has 10 points, Interview has 10 points, Demonstration Teaching has 15 points and English Communication Skills has also 15 points. This is why private teachers chose to stay for how many years teaching in a private school in order for them to gain more points in teaching experience. In fact, teaching experience is very important. The study of Kini et al. (2016) showed that throughout a teacher's career, teaching experience is positively related with student achievement. The advantages of teaching experience will be most realized when teachers are carefully recruited and properly prepared when they enter the teaching field, as well as extensively supervised and thoroughly assessed prior to attaining tenure.

This study revealed that private teachers are experiencing financial constraints during global crisis. Countries all across the world faced problems as a result of the Corona 19 Pandemic. This pandemic causes the global economy to suffer a recession, causing financial hardships for all individuals. Private teachers are now in a dilemma, not only in educational matters, as well as in terms of their financial demands in the wake of pandemic. The findings of this study supports the study of Jaine (2021) showed the shift to online education has increased the inequalities between private and public institutions. It is found out that private teachers were not paid on time and they were receiving lesser salary compare to public teachers. It is showed that some private schools were forced to close due to few enrollees and it affected the salary of private teachers. This study also revealed that private teachers are experiencing mental health issues amidst this pandemic. Private teachers are dealing with psychological and emotional health concerns while they carry out their duties in the midst of andemic. Challenges in their work, family concerns, and personal challenges affected their mental health. This supports the study of Lizana et al. (2021) showed a decline in teachers' quality of life throughout the pandemic. Their study investigated some of the detrimental effects of the COVID-19 pandemic on the mental and physical health of teachers. It showed that the mental health issues by the teachers were attributed to job stress as a result of working remotely, motions of uncertainty, loneliness, and worry that the pandemic and its associated confinements would intensify. This study also revealed that private teachers are working beyond their contract which they consider as one of their challenges. According to Elton (2021) discussed that employment contracts are essential both for the employee and the employer. It binds both sides to carry out their obligations and responsibilities. An employment contract will establish a solid foundation for protecting both the parties' interests as well as the employee's unique position in the firm.

The basic responsibility of an employee is always to work for the employer, and the company should pay the employee based on the amount of work completed within a specific time limit. In connection the study of Isaksson (2010) showed that there is a need to follow by the employer the written contract with their employees in order to build the passion and commitment of their employees on their jobs. This study also revealed that private teachers are Lack of Teaching Resources amidst pandemic which is caused of financial constraints. It is suggested by the participants to at least the government should give a subsidy for the private teachers in order for them to

cope on the demands of distance education amidst pandemic. This study also revealed that private teachers are experiencing problem on their relationship with their school heads. The study of Whitehead, Boschee and Decker (2013) reiterate that when teachers and principals work together and build trust, students face higher academic achievements and have a stronger feeling of well-being. In connection, the study of Chombo (2020) showed that principals must have a positive working connection in order to function successfully and to sustain a healthy professional relationship, solidarity, respect, commitment, and communication among teachers. Indeed, private teachers are also contributors in the growth and development of the Philippine Economy, yet they feel less prioritized as compared to public teachers. Private teachers are also in a dilemma on how to cope on the impact of covid-19 pandemic.

IMPLICATIONS

Based on the findings, the following practical applications are suggested: There is a need for the national government to address also the needs of private teachers amidst pandemic. The national government may also consider to give subsidy to the private schools as an intervention to the financial constraints faced by private teachers amidst pandemic. For private schools, they must follow the minimum wage policy as part of the rights of employees and in order avoid complaints. For private school teachers, they may consider to have a budget plan to help themselves in spending their money wisely and to assure that they have enough budget for a month. Private school institutions may also conduct a program in many ways to cater the problems of their employees in terms of mental health issues. A contract agreement must be followed by both parties, the schools and teachers. To avoid issues, the Human Resource Management must clearly indicate in the contract agreement the expected responsibilities of the teachers. Private schools shall find ways on how to address the problems of their teachers in terms teaching resources to make more effective the teaching and learning process amidst pandemic. It is also recommended for the school administrators to maintain good relationships with their teachers to enhance their confidence and commitment in doing their duties. It is also recommended for the future researchers to look for the coping mechanisms of private teachers on their problems encountered, as well their suggestions and recommendations in improving teaching and learning process in online distance education.

REFERENCES

- Altun, M. (2017). The Effects of Teacher Commitment on Student Achievement: A Case Study in Iraq. *International Journal of Academic Research in Business and Social Sciences*. 7. 10.6007/IJARBS/v7-i11/3475.
- Bao, W. (2020). COVID-19 and online teaching in higher education: A case study of Peking University. *Human Behavior and Emerging Technologies*. <https://doi.org/10.1002/hbe2.191>
- Bashir, S., Bajwa, M. & Rana, S. (2014). Teacher as a Role Model and Its Impact on the Life of Female Students. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.29121/granthaalayah.v1.i1.2014.3081>
- Beauchamp, C. & Thomas, L. (2009). Understanding teacher identity: An overview of issues in the literature and implications for teacher education. *Cambridge Journal of Education*, 39(2), 175-189.
- Chombo, S.C. (2020). The Importance of Good Working Relationships between Principals and School Board Members in Zambezi Region, Namibia.
- DepEd. (2020). DepEd prepares Self-Learning Modules for education's new normal. <https://www.deped.gov.ph/2020/07/02/deped-prepares-self-learning-modules-for-educations-new-normal/>
- DepEd. (2020). DepEd Teacher 1 Hiring Guidelines for SY 2020-2021. <https://www.teacherph.com/deped-hiring-guidelines/>
- Dela Fuente, J.A. (2021). Implementing inclusive education in the Philippines. College teacher experiences with deaf students. *Issues in Educational Research*, 31(1), 94-110. <http://www.iier.org.au/iier31/dela-fuente.pdf>
- Dela Fuente, J.A. (2019). Driving Forces of Students' Choice in Specializing Science: A Science Education Context in the Philippines Perspective. *The Normal Lights*, 13(2), 225-250.
- Elton, W. (2021). The Importance of an Employment Contract. <https://zegal.com/blog/post/importance-of-employment-contract/>

- Gilal, F.G., Channa, N.A., Gilal, N.G., Gilal, R.G. & Shah, S. (2019). Association between a teacher's work passion and a student's work passion: a moderated mediation model. *Psychology Research and Behavior Management*, 12, 889–900. <https://doi.org/10.2147/PRBM.S212004>
- Isaksson, Kerstin & De Cuyper, Nele & Bernhard-Oettel, Claudia & De Witte, Hans. (2010). The role of the formal employment contract in the range and fulfilment of the psychological contract: Testing a layered model. *European Journal of Work and Organizational Psychology - EUR J WORK ORGAN PSYCHOL.* 19. 696-716. 10.1080/13594320903142617.
- Jain, S., Lall, M. & Singh, A. (2021). Teachers' Voices on the Impact of COVID-19 on School Education: Are Ed-Tech Companies Really the Panacea? *Contemporary Education Dialogue*, 18(1), 58–89. <https://doi.org/10.1177/0973184920976433>
- Kini, T. & Podolsky, A. (2016). *Does Teaching Experience Increase Teacher Effectiveness? A Review of the Research* (Palo Alto: Learning Policy Institute,).
- Kopelman, J.L. & Rosen, H.S. (2016). Are Public Sector Jobs Recession-proof? Were They Ever? *Public Finance Review*, 44(3), 370–396. <https://doi.org/10.1177/1091142114565042>
- Lizana, P.A., Vega-Fernandez, G., Gomez-Bruton, A., Leyton, B. & Lera, L. (2021). Impact of the COVID-19 Pandemic on Teacher Quality of Life: A Longitudinal Study from before and during the Health Crisis. *Int. J. Environ. Res. Public Health*, 18, 3764. <https://doi.org/10.3390/ijerph18073764>
- Na, Z. (2015). Taking Teaching as a Calling: The Significance and Practice of Gratitude in a Teacher's Career. *International Journal for Innovation Education and Research*, 3(7), 71–75. <https://doi.org/10.31686/ijer.vol3.iss7.396>
- Narinasamy I. & Logeswaran A.K. (2015). Teacher As Moral Model – Are We Caring Enough? *World Journal of Education*. <http://dx.doi.org/10.5430/wje.v5n6p1>
- Serin, H. (2017). The Role of Passion in Learning and Teaching. *International Journal of Social Sciences and Educational Studies*. 4. 60-64. 10.23918/ijsses.v4i1p60.
- UNESCO. (2020). COVID-19 Educational Disruption and Response. <https://en.unesco.org/covid19/educationresponse>
- Whitehead, B.M., Boschee, F. & Decker, R.H. (2013). *The Principal: Leadership for a Global Society*. Thousand Oaks, CA: SAGE Publications, Inc. <https://doi.org/10.4135/9781544308609>